

**PRESSURES AT WORK AND ITS IMPACTS ON PUBLIC HEALTH
SERVICES: CASE STUDY OF MEDICAL-SURGICALS SERVICES OF UHC
OF TLEMCCEN-ALGERIA**

**PRESSIONS AU TRAVAIL ET IMPACTS SUR LES PRESTATIONS DES
SERVICES DE SANTÉ PUBLIQUE : ÉTUDE DU CAS DES URGENCE
MÉDICO-CHIRURGICALES DU CHU DE TLEMCCEN-ALGÉRIE**

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ABSTRACT

Employees in healthcare institutions are subject to work pressures, especially those assigned to emergency services. The main aim of this present research is to identify the impact of work pressures on health service outcomes of the staff in medical-surgical service of Dr. Tidjani Damerdji Tlemcen University Hospital center (UHC). Data collection process is carried out by means of a survey as a research instrument submitted to 139 workers. The results of the study were quantitatively and qualitatively analyzed based on two tools namely SPSS program version 20 and Statistica version 8. Results revealed that the performance of the staff is affected by both individual and organizational pressures.

KEY WORDS: Healthcare management, Human Resources Performance, Work pressures, Medical-chirurgical service

RESUME

Les employés de santé sont soumis à des pressions au travail, en particulier le personnel des urgences médico-chirurgicales. L'objectif principal de la présente recherche est d'identifier l'impact des pressions du travail sur les bilans des activités du personnel affecté au service médico-chirurgical de CHU Dr Tidjani Damerdji de Tlemcen. Le processus de collecte des données a été effectué au moyen d'un questionnaire soumis à 139 fonctionnaires. Les résultats de l'étude ont été analysés quantitativement et qualitativement à l'aide de deux outils : SPSS(v20) et de Statistica (v8). Les résultats ont révélé que le rendement du personnel est affecté par les pressions d'ordre individuelles et organisationnelles.

MOTS-CLES : Management de santé ; Performance des ressources humaines ; Pressions au travail ; Service médico-chirurgical.

INTRODUCTION

Our world today witnesses many developments in different spheres of human life. The effects of globalization on market economy entail the need to change in the culture of society and inventions in technology. This ongoing process has forced the organization to cope with demand of our global age both at the organizational structure or the human resource levels. Recently, there is an increasing interest in labor pressure due to the growing conviction that this latter affects the worker's health, productivity, and the integrity of organizational behavior in all aspects related to the performance of the organization's human resources. This can also be explained by the fact that they represent the internal aspect that can be controlled and addressed, in contrast to external pressures such as economic, political, social and other pressures that can be out of the scope of the organization.

The main purpose of this research is to identify and analyze the variables that cause the feeling of pressure among many workers of the Emergency department at Tlemcen Hospital which lead to negative impact on their performance.

Workplace stress has become a global concern for all managers and officials as stress in some workgroups has become an epidemic.

In Algeria, managers, doctors and nurses, security agents, have been identified as the most vulnerable to workplace stress.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many previous studies were examined during the preparation of the theoretical framework of the study, which are relevant to the current scope, thus, this part is based on the review of the parameters that were focused on, their procedures, their tools and their most important results:

2.1 Abdelkarim, Maamoun and Nabila, Bouafia., (2018), Psychological combustion and its relationship to the quality of life of night teams workers in medical emergencies.

The aim of this study was to investigate the nature of the relationship between psychological combustion and the quality of the night shift workers life in the Department of Medical Urgencies. The Cristina Maslach ,1982 scale was used (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, personal achievement), MBI (Self-Combustion and Quality of Life Scale).

A random sample of 80 general practitioners, department heads and nurses were used.

The results of the study showed that there are:

- A relationship between self-combustion and the quality of life of night shift workers.
- Night shift workers at the Medical Emergency Service suffer from a high level of combustion.

2.2 Mohannad Aburuz,(2013), The impact of stress on job satisfaction for nurses in King Fahad Specialist Hospital-Dammam-KSA.

This study aimed to determine the main stressors affecting nurses and its relationship with job satisfaction in King Fahad Specialist hospital of Saudi Arabia. A descriptive correlational cross-sectional design was used on a convenience sample of 213 nurses using expanded nursing stress and job satisfaction scales.

2.3 The Study of Regina O Donovan et al.,(2013),The effect of stress on health and its implications for nursing.

This article at identifying the effect of stress on health and its relationship to nursing. Stress is seen as a negative feeling affecting people's health either physically and/or psychologically. However, stress is a normal part of life and considered necessary to increase functional capacity.

2.4 The Study of J-M,R Stacciarini and B-T, Tróccoli, (2004), Occupational stress and constructive thinking: Health and job satisfaction.

This study aimed to identify that Stress at workplace is often referred to as “occupational stress”. The basic rationale underpinning the concept is that the work situation has certain demands, and that problems in meeting these can lead to illness or psychological distress. Occupational stress is a major health problem for both individual employees and organizations, and

can lead to burnout, illness, labour turnover, absenteeism, poor morale and reduced efficiency and performance. Hence, stress is considered as one of the contributing factors that influenced the efficiency, absenteeism, increase in health care costs and other unfavourable results that associated with specific situations, characteristics of the work environment, and individual perceptions and reactions in the context of the workplace.

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND HYPOTHESES

In attempt to clarify the relationship between work pressure and worker’s performance; this general research question has been raised:

To what extent do work pressures affect the performance of emergency department staff?

This general research question has been broken down into sub-inquiries:

- What are the sources of work pressure that affect the performance of employees?
- Does the pressure of work have a statistically significant impact on the performance of workers in the emergency department?

In an endeavor to attain reliable answers to the research questions, the following hypotheses have been formulated:

- ✓ **H.1:** there is a statistically significant relationship between individual work stress sources and employee's performance.
- ✓ **H.2:** there is a statistically significant relationship between job-related stress sources and employee's performance.
- ✓ **H.3:** there is a statistically significant relationship between organizational stress sources and employee's performance.
- ✓ **H.4:** there is a statistically significant relationship between physical environment stress sources and employee's performance.

4. THE OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study set out to:

- To create a theoretical framework that covers all the concepts of work pressure and professional performance.
- To learn about the impacts of work pressure on the performance of the emergency department staff in the Emergency department of the hospital of Tlemcen.
- To find ways to improve the performance of employees in the emergency department and thus facilitate the task of its management.

5. PROCEDURES AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1 THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This present work is a significant endeavor to study the current working conditions and their effects on the employees' performance in the Emergency department at the hospital of Tlemcen. In this respect, this research raises both individuals and organizational awareness of the feasibility of analyzing and studying them.

This study will be also beneficial to the students, instructors, and researchers in healthcare management as it is linked to a multidisciplinary approach where the psychological, physiological and behavioral aspects were studied.

5.2 THE STUDY APPROACH

This current study is based on a descriptive and analytical approach in which qualitative data is opted for through the administration of a survey as the main research instrument. Its aim is to investigate and examine the variables that affect the feeling of pressure among many workers of the Emergency department at Tlemcen Hospital. The variables are classified in two four categories which are: individual sources of stress, job related sources of stress, organizational sources of stress, and physical environment.

Figure N°01: shows the theoretical model of the study:

Source: Prepared by the researches

5.3 SAMPLE POPULATION

The sample population consists of 139 employees at the emergency service of UHC Tlemcen; it includes medical, paramedical, pharmacists and administrative workers. In this respect, a cluster sampling has been opted for to obtain the generalizability of the results to the entire population.

5.4 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The scope of this investigation is a descriptive analytical study which is mostly based on a questionnaire submitted to 139 workers of the emergency department at the university hospital of Tlemcen. Moreover, the process of data collection and analysis is limited to approximately one month which makes the present research a challenging task for the research to include other departments, research tools, layers of analysis.

6. RESULTS ANALYSIS

The process of data analysis was carried out by means of two statistical tools SPSS program and Statistica program version 8

The SPSS program version 20 is used to calculate the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the four dimensions which are:

1. Individual sources of stress;
2. job-related sources of stress;
3. organizational sources of stress;
4. Physical environment sources of stress.

In addition to this, Statistica program version 8 is used to examine the methods of analysis used in this experiment as well as data analysis. In this respect, exploratory factor analysis is used to first identify a small number of factors that explain the observed correlations among the variables. Thus, it was conducted throughout two steps. The first one deals with two tests namely the Bartlett sphericity and KMO to make sure that the data form a sufficiently coherent set of meaningful dimensions. The second one, on the other hand, deals with Principal Component Analysis to ensure that the scale measures what is supposed to measure. The table below attempts to summarize the Principal component Analysis:

Table 1. A Summary of the Principal Component Analysis

Latent variables	N° of item	\bar{x}	σ	Cronbach α	KMO	Total Variance	F Fisher	Bartlett sphericity χ^2 -2
Individual work stress sources	6	2.103	1.12	0.802	0.796	58.07	5.13	55.9
Job-Related work stress sources	7	2.03	1.10	0.710	0.792	64.27	41.02	103.47
Organizational work stress sources	6	2.564	1.26	0.816	0.801	62.1	37.15	158.12
Environment Work stress sources	5	2.07	0.83	0.601	0.608	49.43	314.34	153.98
Work performance	8	2.42	0.99	0.895	0.886	77.8	154.08	283.38
TOTAL		2.247	/	/	/	/	/	/

Source: from Statistica Research Data.

In the light of results obtained from this table, the Cronbach's alphas results revealed that the homogeneity of the instrument is satisfactory as the value of the coefficient is at least 0.60, this reflects the internal consistency of the items.

As for the coefficient of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) which seeks to tell us if the correlations between the pairs can be explained by other included variables, The interpretation of the results takes the following logic: 0.80 and more "Excellent", 0.70 and more "Good", 0.60 and more "Poor", 0.50 and over "Miserable", Less than 0.50 "Unacceptable".

Concerning Bartlett sphericity test which aims to calculate the determinant of the matrix of the sums of products and cross-products (S) from which the inter-correlation matrix is derived.

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The table above reveals that the significance value for the most variables "Sig" is significant (probability of error tends to 0.000), which means that the correlation coefficients between the different pairs of variables are not in turn equal to zero. In the population and therefore factor analysis is a relevant choice.

Regarding the explained variance which must be greater than 50 %, as it is shown from the table, all values are greater than 0.5 except for the physical environment work stress sources that it is 49.43 (less than 50%). does not prevent the exploratory study.

7.DISCUSSION AND INTERPRETATION OF THE RESULTS

Through the applied study conducted at the emergency department of the university hospital center Dr Tidjani Damerdji, Tlemcen, the table below is an endeavor to sum up the results:

Table 2: The results of the field study

	Hypotheses	Results
Main hypo	There is a statistically significant relationship between work stress and employees performance	Strong linear correlation estimated by 48.4 %
First hypo	There is a statistically significant relationship between individual work stress sources and employees performance	strong linear correlation estimated by 30, 1%
Sub-hypotheses	There is a statistically significant relationship between personality and employees performance.	low linear correlation estimated by 14.7 %
	There is a statistically significant relationship between age and employees performance.	strong linear correlation estimated by 38, 5 %
	There is a statistically significant relationship between gender and employees performance.	low linear correlation estimated by 3,5 %
second hypo	There is a statistically significant relationship between job-related stress sources (work nature, role conflict, workload) and employee's performance	low linear correlation estimated by 10 %

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Sub-hypotheses	There is a statistically significant relationship between work nature and employees performance.	low linear correlation estimated by 5,1 %
	There is a statistically significant relationship between role conflict and employees performance.	low linear correlation estimated by 12 %
	There is a statistically significant relationship between workload and employees performance.	low linear correlation estimated by 2.1 %
Third hypo	There is a statistically significant relationship between organizational stress sources (work relationships, supervision, carrier development) and employee's performance	strong linear correlation estimated by 36.8 %
Sub-hypotheses	There is a statistically significant relationship between work relationships and employees performance.	strong linear correlation estimated by 31.3 %
	There is a statistically significant relationship between supervision and employees performance.	low linear correlation estimated by 2.62%
	There is a statistically significant relationship between carrier development and employees performance.	low linear correlation estimated by 5.5
fourth hypo	There is a statistically significant relationship between physical environment stress sources (workplace design, safety, cleanness) and employee's performance.	low linear correlation estimated by 6.4 %
Sub-hypotheses	There is a statistically significant relationship between workplace design and employees performance.	low inverse linear correlation estimated by 8.3 %
	There is a statistically significant relationship between safety and employees performance.	No correlation

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	There is a statistically significant relationship between cleanness and employees performance	low inverse correlation estimated by 7.4 %
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Source : from the SPSS Research Data

The most important conclusions reached by the field research on the problems of working pressure and their impacts on the performance of the human resource are as summarized in the following way:

a) There is a correlation between the hypothesis of the research and the results reached because there is an inverse relationship between the pressures of work and the performance of the human resource.

b) Employees also suffer from problems related to the nature of work, which are listed below:

- Increasing the burdens and responsibilities of employees due to multiple actions.
- Blurred objectives and work procedures.

c) We also record the other type of suffering which refer to the problems of working conditions that include:

- The imbalance in the provision of certain physical and special working conditions: adaptation, lighting and others;
- Suffering from frequent noise and overcrowding in the workplace;
- Poor design of emergency department.
- In the light of the findings obtained from the problems experienced by workers and the pressures they suffer during the exercise of their function, and the purpose of improving working conditions and then reduce the pressure and improve their performance, we recommend the following suggestions:
 - Focusing on the employees' training based on intensive and extensive courses inside and outside the hospital in order to achieve growth, development and innovation in the working methods;
 - More attention should be paid to the workers and the pressures that affect them even if they have not a direct influence on their performance;

- Searching for hidden and unknown pressures that may affect the performance of workers and find solutions;
- The workers' internal motivation improves their performance, so the organization must delegate tasks according to competences.
- Improvement of the internal working conditions in order to increase worker generosity and thus increase efficiency in performance
- The organization should use the positive points of work pressure in its interest by devising new ways to raise the employees' performance.
- Commitment to fairness and objectivity in evaluating employees' performance and clarity regarding wages and incentives.

In order to test the hypotheses of our empirical model on the relationship between work stress and employees performance, the relations between the variables were studied by using the method of structural equations which is Statistica version 8 software.

The data obtained from the survey conducted on the sample population at the emergency department of the university hospital center Dr Tidjani Damerdji, Tlemcen, results revealed the existence of a positive and significant relationship between the different variables of our structural model with the exception of the relationship between the job-related stress sources, physical environment stress sources and employees performance.

The results are satisfactory because the structural links between the variables were significant (less than 0.05) this indicates that the individual work stress, organizational stress sources influence more strongly on the employees performance than job-related stress sources and physical environment stress sources. This can be explained by the fact that the sources of pressure (job-related stress sources, physical environment stress sources) do not have any significant effect on the performance of workers in the emergency department, but they may have an impact in another area, for example, administration.

Regarding the rest of the hypotheses related to the influence of individual work stress, organizational stress sources on the employees' performance, results revealed the positive influence between the various variables mentioned, which validates the hypotheses of our model under consideration.

CONCLUSION

The introduction of the concept of appraisal suggested that stress was best understood (J OGDEN. (2007:236), as an interaction between the individual and the outside world. Accordingly, a stress response would be elicited if an event were appraised as stressful. Once appraised as a stressor

Work pressure is considered as a component of the internal environment of the organization that might affect the organizational behavior of individuals and the performance of human resources in general. It should be added, however, that it is not possible to find an organization; whether it produces goods or provides services free from labor pressures, it is not easy to control "work stress. It is only enough that the organization possesses the required competencies to reduce them, and that, of course, totally depends on the effectiveness of the administration and the way of supervising individuals through achieving their integration and affiliation with their organization. This latter creates a sense of loyalty and sincerity in achieving the goals set for everyone and the organization in general.

ANNEXES:

- **Confirmatory factor analysis**

The principle of confirmatory factor analysis is to verify if the theoretical model is not different from the observed model, in order to make this verification, indicators are calculated to measure the quality of the adjustment between the theoretical model and the observed model.

- **1. Adjustment indices:**

The adjustment indices are classified into three groups:

i. Absolute adjustment indices:

These indices make it possible to evaluate the degree of adjustment of the proposed theoretical model, with a structural model (the empirical model).

ANNEXES 1: (4 tables)

- **Table 1:** Absolute adjustment indices table.

The indices	GLS-ML
Chi_2	1034.37
Degré de liberté DF	430
Niveau p	0.000
RMS Résidus Standardisés	0,0805
Steiger-Lind RMSEA Index	0,088
(GFI). Joreskog and Sorbom	0,660
(AGFI). Joreskog	0,608

Source: Based on Statistica program outputs

ii. Incremental indices:

These indices were constructed in comparison with a basic model, which is the model of independence, its interval is between 0 and 1, the objective of this index focuses on the selection of the model for which these indicators are close to 1 and greater than 0.9. Below are the indices used in the estimation of the model.

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- **Table 2:** Incremental Indices Table.

The indices	GLS-ML
Bentler-Bonett Normed Fit Index, NFI	0,617
Bentler-Bonett Non-Normed Fit Index	0,575
Bentler Comparative Fit Index	0,624
Bollen's Rho	0,561
Bollen's Delta	0,441

Source: Based on Statistica program outputs

iii. The parsimony indexes

- **Table 3:** Parsimony indices table.

The indices	ML
James, Mulaik & Brett Parcimonieuse Fit Index	0, 765
Ch2 /DF	2.40

Source: Based on Statistica program outputs

(Ch2 / DF) is between 2 and 5, so its value is good.

- **Tableau 4:** Coefficient of Regression of Structural Relations

Variables latentes	Parameter Estimate β_i	Prob level
(INDIVID)-64->(PERFORM)	0,793	0,000
(JOBREL)-65->(PERFORM)	0,182	0,061
(ORGANIZ)-66->(PERFORM)	0,566	0,001
(ENVIRM)-67->(PERFORM)	0,134	0,065
(ZETA1) -->(PERFORM)	0,000	0,245

Source: Based on Statistica program outputs

From the above table, we conclude the structural equation of the model as follows:

Performance = 0,793 INDIVID+0,182 JOBREL+ 0,566 ORGANIZ+ 0,134 ENVIRM+ 0,000

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16	The work assigned is far from my experience and skills					
17	The nature of my work requires high concentration due to the tasks I do to keep the patient safe.					
18	In general cases I have difficulty convincing patients and their companions					
20	The nature of my work imposes the responsibility of maintaining the health of patients which increases the intensity of stress					
Thirdly: Organizational sources						
21	My relationships with my colleagues at work are generally good					
22	My relationships with my superiors are good					
23	In general, my relationships at work don't make me a source of pressure.					
24	There's always a direct supervisor back when I need to.					
25	My supervisor helps me to accomplish my daily tasks.					
26	The supervisor of my work is always guiding me					
27	I feel unable to progress in my career					
28	It is difficult to achieve my ambitions in my workplace					
29	Job opportunities are linked to vacancies and not efficient					
Fourthly: Environment sources						
30	Bad design of the emergency department causes me a strain.					
31	Congestion is increasing in the emergency department due to its bad design					
32	I suffer from poor lighting and ventilation at the department level.					
33	Safety and security conditions are available at my workplace					
34	I am afraid of infection from infectious diseases due to pollution and lack of hygiene					

- Rubric two: Work Performance

Firstly: Task performance						
35	I am committed to duties and instructions that govern my work					
36	I plan well for work tasks before implementation					
37	I execute the required works efficiently and effectively.					
Secondly: Adaptive performance						

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38	The institution in which I work performs training courses for employees in all wires.					
39	There are opportunities in my workplace to develop my skills for career progression.					
40	The foundation's formative courses help me in my career					
Thirdly: Contextual performance						
41	I can dialogue, manage discussion and communicate with colleagues					
42	My superiors are satisfied with my performance at work.					
43	I'm working on creating and maintaining positive relationships with my coworkers.					
Fourthly: Counterproductive work behavior						
44	There are violent actions in my workplace that limit my performance.					
45	I notice that there are bad behaviors in my workplace (theft, fraud, sexual harassment....)					
46	I notice an administrative dropout in my workplace					

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A. According to your opinion, what are the pressures of work you are facing?

.....

B. Do you think the organization's management is working to provide a stress-free working environment? and how?

.....

C. How do you evaluate your daily stress level? *Low* *Medium* *High*

D. How do you classify your occupational stress symptoms? *Psy* *Behavioral*
Physical

Rubric Three: Personal information

Gender/ *Male:* *Female:*

Age: *Under 30 y.o* *Between 31-40 y.o* *Between 41-50 y.o* *Older than 50*

Social status: *Single* *Married:* *Divorced:* *Widow:*

Level of study: *Primary school* *Secondary school* *High school* *University*

Experience in work: *Less than 5 years* *Between 5-10 years* *Between 11-20*
More than 21 y

Current Position: *Chief Service:* *Doctor:* *Paramedical:*

Coordinator: *Administrator:* *Biologist:*

Security agent: *Clean Worker:* *Pharmaceutics:*

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on SPSS program outputs.

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